

SWOT-BASED STRATEGIC ANALYSIS FOR SUSTAINABLE UTILIZATION OF LATERITE ORE DEPOSITS OF SINDH, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Laterite ore deposits in Sindh represent an important yet underutilized mineral resource of Pakistan. The mining of laterite in Sindh is still at a developing stage, often carried out through small-scale and manual extraction without the adoption of modern mechanized techniques. This results in low recovery, poor ore quality, and considerable material loss. In this study, the SWOT analysis index was formulated to reflect the specific characteristics of enhancing the utilization of laterite ore deposit. The data for the SWOT analysis was obtained through a combination of expert opinions, and relevant literature sources. The SWOT index framework consisted of Internal factors that possess elements for Strengths (S) and Weakness (W) while external factors have elements with Opportunity (O) and Threats (T). A total of 19 elements were categorized in the SWOT analysis for the strategic sustainable utilization of laterite ore industry. The analysis of SWOT elements revealed that the strengths of laterite ore reserves in province Sindh hold the higher significance receiving the weight of 0.35. Threats ranked second with second highest weight 0.32. Weaknesses and Opportunity were ranked third and fourth, with weights of 0.18 and 0.15 respectively. The results highlight the elements in strength factor had highest weight, showing the potential of laterite deposit of Sindh, Pakistan. However, Threats in the development of laterite industry can also not be ignored. Therefore, robust strategies with proper policies could assist in sustainable growth of laterite deposit in Sindh, Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

Laterite ore is considered as significant resource of iron, aluminum, nickel, and other important trace metals, which are formed because of the prolonged sediments weathering of mafic and ultramafic rocks

with the support of tropical climatic conditions (Valeton, 1994). Laterites have been widely considered as a strategic raw material obtained from mining activities in the cement, metallurgical

industries, environmental and construction sectors globally (Santha Kumar et al., 2022). Moreover, in the countries like Indonesia, India and Philippines utilization of laterite has played an important role in their industrial development particular focus on iron and nickel extraction. In country like Pakistan the laterite utilization remains unexplored even though growing demand for the indigenous raw materials especially laterite to support infrastructure and industrialization has increased (Khan et al., 2016).

Sindh province is in the southern part of the country and endowed with high grade deposits of laterite ore. These laterite deposits, although still not fully exploited as per their potential. Presence of laterite ore represents an asset that might reduce reliance on other imported minerals. The abundance presence of laterite ore deposit in Sindh province offers a great opportunity for its integration into various industries which includes road construction, cement manufacturing and wastewater treatment (Malkani et al., 2017). However, increasing the environmental and industrial burden faced by country like Pakistan, the strategic utilization of indigenous laterite ore is

crucial step for the sustainable development with special focus on economic growth.

Based on the previous studies (Cyriaque Kaze et al., 2022; Fan et al., 2024; Jain & Kalamdhad, 2020; Kamagate et al., 2018; Nguyen et al., 2020) the potential utilization of laterite ore globally is shown in Figure 1. However, the use of indigenous laterite ore in Pakistan has been confined to minor utilization, primarily in road stabilization, construction with limited industrial potential such as cement industry (Malkani et al., 2017). Due to lack of advanced mineral upgradation and processing facilities and research and development (R&D) have restricted from capitalizing the full benefits of the indigenous laterite ore (Bawani, Anjum, et al., 2025). However, various regional countries recently established industries based on lateritic ore which help them to meet their domestic needs but at the same time also contribute to their export potential (Elias, 2002). Therefore, the urgent need to develop a comprehensive strategy for the country like Pakistan for the utilization of lateritic ore.

Figure 1. Utilization of laterite ore

In addition, the rise in global demand for critical minerals such as cobalt and nickel is also rapidly increasing as these minerals are extensively used in batteries and electric vehicles as clean energy technologies and storage systems for renewable energy (Gielen 2021). Lateritic ores are also considered as major sources for the recovery of iron, cobalt and nickel, making this resource as strategically important in the transition of low-carbon economies (Shannak et al., 2024). By developing indigenous laterite extraction and beneficiation technologies in Sindh, Pakistan may align with global trends in development of green technology for contributing to the achievement of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Despite considering these opportunities for laterite ores, the exploitation of these resources in Sindh is full of challenges. The laterite ore is typically of low grade in Sindh, requiring energy-intensive and cost-effective processing methods. These methods include physical separation, chemical treatment and biological treatment methods (Bawani, Anjum, et al., 2025; Schippers et al., 2025; Zappala et al., 2024) as shown in Figure 2. Physical separation methods are widely applied in the upgrading of both mineral resources (an inorganic substance) including laterite ores (Bawani, Anjum, et al., 2025) and organic materials such as coal (Bawani, Arol, et al., 2025; Bawani et al., 2023), mainly to remove impurities and improve grade. In contrast, chemical and biological methods recover targeted elements by

breaking down or altering the mineral crystal structure through leaching or microbial activity, but poses environmental concerns (Schippers et al., 2025; Zappala et al., 2024). Environmental risks associated with laterite mining and beneficiation, such as soil erosion, deforestation, and water contamination might also pose significant threats to ecosystems and ultimately the local communities (Abdulazeez. et al., 2024). Therefore, any strategic plan for laterite utilization must incorporate sustainable mining practices, environmental safeguards, and community participation to ensure long-term viability. Various researchers have used

SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis for the planning of agricultural (Brohi et al., 2020), mining (Jiskani et al., 2020) and industrial projects (Kalwar et al., 2018) in Sindh, Pakistan. As SWOT framework is considered as one of the most reliable techniques. In this circumstance, a SWOT based analysis provides comprehensive framework for the assessment of the potential for indigenous laterite deposits in the Sindh province of Pakistan. In addition, identification of the external and internal factors which influence the strategic utilization of laterite aims to develop the strategic insights for industries, policymakers, and researchers.

Figure 2. Beneficiation techniques for laterite

The focus of the study is to conduct a SWOT analysis of laterite deposits in Sindh for better strategic planning of these resources. SWOT approach is crucial for harnessing the untapped potential of indigenous laterite deposits while considering the associated challenges, thereby paving the way for its integration into Pakistan’s industrial and environmental management strategies.

2. Research Methodology

2.1 Study Area

Laterite iron ore deposits in Sindh represent an important yet underutilized mineral resource of Sindh, Pakistan. These deposits are primarily located

in the Nagarparkar, Lakhra, Jhamphir, Makli Hills, Sonahri Dhand, Jhal Dhand and Noriabad region (Malkani et al., 2017) as shown in Figure 3. The geological surveys reveal that the lateritic ore exist in these areas are due to the prolonged weathering of its parent lithologies due to the tropical and subtropical climate regimes thus concentrating iron and contributing towards the leaching of silica and other solvable elements (Jan et al., 2016). The ore is normally reddish-brown in color, have a fine to medium grained texture and contain a variety of iron-oxide minerals such as goethite, hematite and limonite with a variable concentration. Laterite iron ore occurred near the surface as well as in shallow

sub-surface formations in Sindh which can be extracted with the removal of topsoil using small-

scale mining projects.

Figure 3. Locations of the laterite deposits of Sindh

The proximity of these deposits to major transport routes enhances their economic viability, allowing for easier integration into local and regional supply chains. Laboratory analyses of lateritic ore of Sindh suggest that the ore is suitable for applications in cement manufacturing, road construction and in the preparation of water treatment coagulant, while beneficiation processes could further increase its industrial value. Despite its potential, the exploitation of lateritic iron ore in Sindh remains minimal due to limited technological development, low investment in mining infrastructure, and lack of awareness about its economic significance. With appropriate policy support and sustainable mining practices, the lateritic iron ore deposits of Sindh could contribute significantly to the provinces and the country’s industrial and economic growth.

In this study, the SWOT analysis index was formulated to reflect the specific characteristics of

enhancing the utilization of laterite ore deposit. The strategic planning for sustainable utilization was performed based upon the nature of industry, production dynamics, growth potential, and the challenges it faces (Benzaghta et al., 2021). The SWOT index framework consists of Internal factors that possess elements for Strengths (S) and Weakness (W) while external factors have elements with Opportunity (O) and Threats (T). The data for the SWOT analysis was obtained through a combination of expert opinions, and relevant literature sources. For strategic planning various factors and elements were identified through literature survey, then was converted into questionnaire. Experts with sound knowledge and experience in the mineral industry were selected for the study. A total of 19 elements were categorized in the SWOT analysis for the strategic sustainable utilization of laterite ore industry. These identified nineteen critical factors

under the four components of the SWOT framework are reported in Figure 4. For the Internal components Strength (S) with five key elements were identified as S1, S2, S3, S4 & S5, while for Weakness 4 elements were identified as W1, W2, W3 & W4. On the contrary, for external components 5 key elements for Opportunity (O) were identified as O1, O2, O3, O4 & O5, while threats (T) with four elements were identified as T1, T2, T3, T4 & T5. The description of these elements is presented in Table 1. The SWOT Index was developed for the strategic planning to develop sustainable laterite ore industry of Sindh, Pakistan.

2.1.1 Strength

Strength is considered as the first component of the SWOT framework, addressing the first research question by identifying factors that provide a competitive advantage for the enhanced utilization of laterite iron deposit as showed in Table 1. Sindh being rich with laterite ore deposit could assist in the socio-economic growth of local communities (Jan et al., 2016). The rise in the laterite utilization would enhance the remote area employment with support to the local wastewater treatment industries. This would lead to a quicker return on investment and an increased profit margin.

2.1.2 Weaknesses

This element is divided into four sub-criteria encompassing factors that may hinder the growth and sustainable utilization of laterite ore deposit. Laterite ore utilization is possible with ore processing industry with low investment and lack of processing plant could potentially hinder the development of laterite deposit (Arinze, 2015). Governmental shortcomings, including the absence of a comprehensive regulatory framework at both federal and provincial levels, have led to procedural delays and discouraged investment, particularly from foreign stakeholders. While dealing with the utilization of ore deposit, one could not undermine the

variation in the quality of ore. Thus, making it huge task for utilization capability. Although deposit of laterite ore in Sindh offers significant potential, persistent economic instability and limited capital accessibility threaten to turn this abundance into a liability.

2.1.3 Opportunity

The third research question was addressed by identifying factors within this element that present promising prospects for the growth of the laterite deposit. High unemployment rates and limited competition from other sectors enable the low-cost human resources for this project. Additionally, small business entrees in this remote area could potentially strengthen the lifestyle of local people (Del Castillo & Dimitrakopoulos, 2019). By generating employment opportunities, industry can also secure a social license to operate. Furthermore, international collaboration particularly within the framework of China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) projects offer potential avenues for financing and investment.

2.1.4 Threats

This final component of the SWOT framework addresses the last research question, focusing on threats and adverse factors that could severely impede the development of the laterite deposit. Political instability and unfavorable geopolitical conditions create significant risks that discourage investment in the sector. Poor infrastructure with technological gaps could potentially threaten the utilization of laterite deposits in Sindh. Additionally, mining operations can have detrimental environmental impacts, including ecosystem degradation and land disturbance (Dimitrakopoulos, 2018). Climate change and global warming threat due to mining operations must be critically considered in planning for the sustainable development of mineral industry (Chalgrı, Memon, Siddiqui, & Shaikh, 2025)

Figure 4. SWOT Analysis Index

Table 1. Strengths, Weakness, Opportunity and Threats (SWOT) description

	Abbreviation	Description
Strength (S)	S1	Potential Reserves
	S2	Application Versatility
	S3	Low Mining Complexity
	S4	Environmental Benefits
	S5	Indigenous Employment
Weakness (W)	W1	Lack of Processing facilities
	W2	Ore quality Variation
	W3	Low investment
	W4	Regulatory and Policy Gaps
Opportunity (O)	O1	Indigenous Industrialization
	O2	Export Market Access
	O3	Small Scale Business entrees
	O4	Research and Development
	O5	Integration with CPEC Projects
Threats (T)	T1	Environmental Restriction
	T2	Technological Gap
	T3	Infrastructure Limitations
	T4	Political instability
	T5	Climate change mitigations

3 Results and Discussion

The SWOT analysis determined using pairwise comparison and corresponding weights presented in Tables (2-5) and Figures (5-6). The SWOT analysis

shows that strengths (0.35) outweigh weaknesses (0.18), reflecting the potential of Sindh’s laterite deposits for industrial utilization. Although threats (0.32) exceed opportunities (0.15), effective

upgradation through physical, chemical, and biological methods can reduce weaknesses and enhance utilization, supporting the sustainable development of laterite resources.

3.1 Internal factors

The calculated weights of the strength factors are presented in Table 2. with the prioritization order of sub-criteria as S5>S1>S2>S3>S4. Indigenous employment (S5) emerges as the most significant strength of development of laterite ore deposit of Sindh weighted 0.12, followed by potential reserves (S1) weighted 0.10, application versatility (S2) and low mining complexity (S3) both weighted 0.05, and Environmental benefits (S4) weighted 0.03. The SWOT analysis revealed that the internal factors, i.e., strengths and weaknesses together account for 0.53 of the total weight. Among these, strengths ranked first (0.35) as shown in Table 2. This suggests that while laterite resources possess considerable inherent advantages, equally significant challenges constrain their exploitation. The significance of these advantages is well supported in literature. Despite the country’s abundant laterite ore reserves, they

remain underutilized in the national socio-economic growth (Bawani, Anjum, et al., 2025). Mining of laterite is also considered as a major source of environmental degradation including water, air, soil pollution with waste generation and ecosystem disruption (Vandana et al., 2024). Therefore, effective reduction of environmental impact of mining activities requires a combination of regulatory, technological and sustainable management strategies (Hilson, 2000).

The strengths primarily derive from the diverse uses of laterite across multiple industries. Laterite is already employed in cement production, ceramics, and as a road base material in Pakistan (X. Ma et al., 2016). Its abundance in Sindh, coupled with high contents of iron, alumina, and silica, makes it a cost-effective raw material. Globally, laterite is recognized as a potential source of iron, nickel, cobalt, and bauxite, feeding into steel, aluminum, and battery production (Xue et al., 2020). Moreover, laterite shows strong adsorption capacity for contaminants such as fluoride, arsenic, and heavy metals, which highlights its application in water purification technologies (Li et al., 2023; B. Ma et al., 2013).

Table 2. Strengths for the laterite industry description

Strength (S)	Weight	Ranking
Potential Reserves (S1)	0.10	2
Application Versatility (S2)	0.05	3
Low Mining Complexity (S3)	0.05	3
Environmental Benefits (S4)	0.03	4
Indigenous Employment (S5)	0.12	1
Total (Strengths)	0.35	

The component weakness (W) is divided into four sub-categories, with the weights of the main factors and sub-factors presented in Figure 5 and Table 3. Lack of processing facilities (W1) rank highest with a weight of 0.09, followed by Variation in ore quality (W2) at 0.06, low investment (W3) at 0.02 and regulatory policy gap (W4) with least 0.01 weight. These weaknesses are from interrelated and systemic challenges across the sector. Government reports also highlight similar gaps, with obsolete technology being the most critical. This technological delay

prevents industry from producing standardized products due to reliance on non-mechanized, outdated methods. Furthermore, the mineral sector suffers from a shortage of qualified and skilled personnel (Dong, 2011). In addition, the application versatility is very low due to complex mineralogy of lateritic ore, as stated by Bawani et al. (2025).

Mining in Sindh remains manual and small-scale, with little adoption of mechanized surface mining methods, resulting in low recovery and poor ore quality. The ore is extracted without adequate

geological surveys or resource estimation, which undermines long-term planning. Additionally, laterite deposits exhibit high moisture content, heterogeneous mineralogy, and significant silica/clay impurities, complicated beneficiation and reducing industrial efficiency (Fan et al., 2024; Malavath et al.,

2013). These weaknesses reflect the technical and infrastructural gaps in current exploitation practices, which limit laterite’s industrial potential in Pakistan despite its natural abundance.

Table 3. Weakness for the laterite industry description

Weakness (W)	Weight	Ranking
Lack of Processing facilities (W1)	0.09	1
Ore quality Variation (W2)	0.06	2
Low investment (W3)	0.02	3
Regulatory and Policy Gaps (W4)	0.01	4
Total (Weakness)	0.18	

Figure 5. Weights for internal factors

3.2 External Factors

The analysis of external factors revealed that opportunity (0.15) are comparatively lower than threats (0.32), as shown in Table 4 and 5. This suggests that, although there are prospects for laterite utilization in Sindh, significant risks such as environmental concerns, global competition, and technological barriers pose considerable challenges. The third factor addresses the external opportunities which can impact positively to the development of laterite industry in Sindh, Pakistan. Based on the computed weights provided in Table 4 and Figure 6, the opportunities rank as industrial wastewater treatment (O1=0.07), Small scale business (O3=0.05), Export Market Access (O2=0.01), Research and Development (O4=0.01), and Integration with CPEC Projects (O5=0.01). As per the location of the laterite, there are various industries that discharge wastewater therefore laterite might be used as

coagulant for the treatment (Arinze, 2015; Malavath et al., 2013). Enhancement of small-scale business in the remote areas due to mining activities is essential thus creating an opportunity for the local people to improve their lifestyle (Benzaghta et al., 2021).

Apart from its direct use, the key opportunities are linked to the beneficiation or upgradation and advanced applications of laterite ore. With the use of beneficiation technologies such as crushing, screening, washing, and magnetic separation, iron and alumina content can be enhanced while reducing silica and clay impurities (Bawani, Anjum, et al., 2025). Beneficiation techniques applied to laterite ores are discussed earlier (Figure 2). For nickel and cobalt bearing laterites, hydrometallurgical approaches such as high-pressure acid leaching (HPAL) and heap leaching have proven effective in extracting valuable metals for stainless steel and clean-energy solutions (Kaya & Topkaya,

2011). Similarly, calcination and reduction roasting methods can upgrade low-grade laterite in Sindh, making it a viable feedstock for cement, iron, and metallurgical industries. These technological advancements present opportunities for Pakistan to

reduce its reliance on imported raw materials and position laterite within green technology value chains such as electric vehicles, renewable energy storage, and geopolymer production (Arinze, 2015).

Table 4. Opportunity for the laterite industry description

Opportunity (O)	Weight	Ranking
Industrial Wastewater Treatment (O1)	0.07	1
Export Market Access (O2)	0.01	3
Small Scale Business Entrees (O3)	0.05	2
Research and Development (O4)	0.01	3
Integration with CPEC Projects (O5)	0.01	3
Total (Opportunity)	0.15	

In the last category, Technological Gap (T2= 0.12) has the highest weight presented in table 5, while on the second rank Environmental Restriction (T1) weighs 0.08. Infrastructure Limitations (T3=0.07) ranked third, climate change mitigations (T4= 0.03) ranked fourth and political instability with least weight 0.02 is at fifth position. The major threat in the development of laterite ore industry is the

technological gap due to underdeveloped countries and lack of interest of government support mineral industry is facing the said issue (Chalgri et al., 2025). Current global changes in the rules and regulations for the environment sustainability could also be a threat for the development of mining activities in Pakistan.

Table 5. Threats for the laterite industry description

Threats (T)	Weight	Ranking
Environmental Restriction (T1)	0.08	2
Technological Gap (T2)	0.12	1
Infrastructure Limitations (T3)	0.07	3
Political instability (T4)	0.02	5
Climate change mitigations (T5)	0.03	4
Total (Threats)	0.32	

Figure 6. Weights for external factors

Furthermore, threats arise from both environmental and economic dimensions. Laterite surface mining can cause land degradation, deforestation, and soil fertility loss, particularly in tropical settings. Global market dynamics, including price fluctuations in nickel and iron and the availability of cheaper substitute raw materials, may undermine the economic viability of laterite exploitation in Sindh. Additionally, the lack of policy support, technology transfer, and sustainable mining regulations increases the risk of unsystematic exploitation and environmental damage. Climate change considerations further necessitate eco-friendly processing to minimize carbon emissions associated with beneficiation and roasting processes.

4 Conclusion

The results highlight the elements in strength factor had highest weight, showing the potential of laterite deposit of Sindh, Pakistan. However, Threats in the development of laterite industry can also not be ignored. It is concluded that the strengths of laterite ore lie in its wide industrial uses, while its weaknesses stem from poor mining and limited beneficiation. With proper beneficiation or upgradation technologies, these weaknesses can be turned into opportunities for advanced applications. While threats such as environmental concerns and market challenges must be carefully managed. Therefore, robust strategies with proper policies could assist in sustainable growth of laterite deposit in Sindh, Pakistan.

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